

The Kinetics of Slow Coagulation. Part I.

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It is well known that Smoluchowski's equation for the rapid coagulation of a colloid proves unsatisfactory when it is extended to cases of slow coagulation. The process of slow coagulation of a colloid is generally autocatalytic in nature where the rate of coagulation is given by the characteristic S-shaped curves.

An examination of the data obtained by Ishizaka (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1913, **83**, 97), Gann (*Koll. Chem. Beih.*, 1916, **8**, 65), Lottermoser (*Kolloid Z.*, 1914, **15**, 145) and others in the light of Smoluchowski's theory, showed that the autocatalytic nature of a coagulation process cannot be explained on the basis of the above theory. Even in cases where the coagulation process has lost its autocatalytic nature, marked divergences from Smoluchowski's theory have been observed. Thus ultra-microscopic measurements of the rate of coagulation by Steacie (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1930, **34**, 1850), Kruyt and van Arkel (*Kolloid Z.*, 1923, **32**, 29) with different colloids have shown that although the process is not autocatalytic in nature, the rate of coagulation is distinctly slower than that required by Smoluchowski's theory. Similar divergences become apparent from an examination of the experimental data of Desai (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1928, **24**, 181).

Westgren and Reitstotter (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1922, **26**, 5371) have pointed out that Smoluchowski's theory should apply only to monodisperse sol. According to them the divergences from the theory are due mainly to (i) polydisperse nature of the colloid, and, (ii) presence of traces of electrolytes in the colloid. In the present paper using Odén's sulphur sol it has been shown that Smoluchowski's theory breaks down even when the sol is monodisperse ; the sol is free from traces of ionogenic impurities, and is so dilute that its coagulation is no longer autocatalytic.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The sample of sulphur sol was prepared by the method given by Bassett and Durrant (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 2933) and from this a sample of monodisperse sol was obtained by the following method. The sol was just made turbid by the addition of a few drops of 2N-NaCl, allowed to stand for sometime, after which the coagulum

was separated by filtration through a Zsigmondy membrane filter. This process was repeated several times and the coagulum obtained during the last fraction was dissolved in distilled water when a clear sol was obtained. It has been shown by Odèn (*Kolloid Z.*, 1911, 8, 186) that the colloid obtained by the above method is a monodisperse sol.

The tyndallmeter described by the author in a previous paper (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 9, 592) has been used for measuring the rate of coagulation of the monodisperse sol using potassium chloride as the coagulating electrolyte. To a measured volume of the sol a known amount of electrolyte was added and this mixture was used on the tyndallmeter. The intensity of the scattered beam was measured at definite intervals of time; the experimental values have been plotted in Figs. 1 and 2. From these figures the times corresponding to the same stage of coalescence of the sol have been obtained and are given in Tables I and II.

FIG. 1.

Light scattering—time curves for conc. sol.

FIG. 2.

Light scattering—time curves for dil. sol.

TABLE I.

Sol concentration = 40 mg. of sulphur per litre.

Curves →	I.	II.	III.	IV.	V.	VI.	Ratio values.				
Electrolyte conc. m.mols./litre. →	110	87.5	75	70	65	60					
Intensity (scale readings).	<i>T</i> (sec.)	<i>T</i> ₁	<i>T</i> ₂	<i>T</i> ₃	<i>T</i> ₄	<i>T</i> ₅	<i>T</i> ₁ / <i>T</i>	<i>T</i> ₂ / <i>T</i>	<i>T</i> ₃ / <i>T</i>	<i>T</i> ₄ / <i>T</i>	<i>T</i> ₅ / <i>T</i>
88.5	9	69	186	366	690	1212	7.6	20.6	40.6	70	194.6
88	12	80	274	456	780	1660	6.6	22.8	38	65	140
87	14	99	290	570	996	...	7.0	20.7	40.7	71.1	...
86	18	117	330	633	1146	...	6.5	18.3	35.1	69.6	...
85	21	134	363	693	1270	...	6.4	17.3	33.2	60.4	...
84	24	150	396	750	1404	...	6.2	16.5	31.2	58.5	...

TABLE II.

Sol concentration = 6.5 mg. of sulphur per litre.

Curves →	I.	II.	III.	IV.	V.	VI.	Ratio values.				
Electrolyte conc. m.mols./litre. →	140	120	110	100	90	80					
Intensity (scale reading).	<i>T</i> (sec.)	<i>T</i> ₁	<i>T</i> ₂	<i>T</i> ₃	<i>T</i> ₄	<i>T</i> ₅	<i>T</i> ₁ / <i>T</i>	<i>T</i> ₂ / <i>T</i>	<i>T</i> ₃ / <i>T</i>	<i>T</i> ₄ / <i>T</i>	<i>T</i> ₅ / <i>T</i>
90	9	18	39	56	126	261	2	4.3	6.2	14.0	29.3
89.5	22	42	96	136	306	690	1.9	4.3	6.1	19.9	31.1
89	36	66	150	216	486	1080	1.9	4.2	6.0	19.5	30.0
88.5	48	87	206	297	672	1464	1.8	4.3	6.1	14.0	30.5
88	66	117	260	378	846	1890	1.8	4.0	5.7	12.8	28.0
87.5	84	140	315	474	1030	...	1.7	3.8	5.6	12.3	...

FIG. 3.

Simultaneously with the above measurements the absorption of light by the same sulphur sol has been followed by an experimental arrangement as shown in Fig. 3. A straight portion of the filament of 60 C. P. lamp was used as the light source. A parallel beam obtained by means of a system of lenses and a suitable aperture was rendered monochromatic by means of Zeiss light filter (designed for the blue mercury line 4359) and after passing through a double cell having two exactly similar compartments was photographed on Ilford process plates having a speed of H. D. 50. One of the compartments of the double cell contained only the colloid, while the other contained the colloid with the added amount of electrolyte. On the photographic plate a pair of lines is obtained; one is due to the beam which has passed through the clear sol, while the other is due to that passing through the sol—electrolyte mixture. The intensity of the pair of lines was next measured by a Zeiss microphotometer. A comparison of the intensities of the pair of lines enables one to determine the rate of coagulation of the colloid as the amount of light absorbed, on which depends the intensity of the lines, is proportional to the rate of coagulation of the sol. It was necessary, however, to keep the experimental conditions exactly the same in every case.

In Figs. 4 and 5 some of the photographs of the lines and copies of the prints obtained on the microphotograph are given.

FIG. 4.

It will be seen that corresponding to any pair of lines A and B, in Fig. 4, a curve with two adjacent peaks C and D (Fig. 5) are obtained on the print of the microphotometer. The difference of the heights between these peaks is proportional to the difference in the intensities of the lines A and B, which in its turn represents the difference in turbidity between the sols in the two compartments of the double cell. In the present experiments these differences between the heights of the peaks for a series of lines obtained at different intervals have been taken as a measure of the stage of coagulation of the sol.

FIG. 5.

To correct for any variation in the intensity at different parts of the straight filament used as the source and also for any difference in the thickness of the walls of the cell, an initial reading was taken when a sample of the same sulphur sol was placed in both the compartments of the double cell and this reading was used as the zero error for the subsequent measurements. The experimental values are given in the Table III.

FIG. 6.

Light absorption—time curve for conc. sol.

TABLE III.

Sol concentration = 40 mg. of sulphur per litre.

Curves →	I.	II.	III.	IV.	V.	VI.	Ratio values.				
Electrolyte conc. in m. mols./litre. →	110	87.5	75	70	64	60					
Diff. in peak height.	240	200	175	165	155	145					
	T (sec.)	T_1	T_2	T_3	T_4	T_5	T_1/T	T_2/T	T_3/T	T_4/T	T_5/T
0.5 cm.	12	66	228	312	696	990	4.4	19	28.5	58	82
1	16	90	306	420	800	1140	5.6	19	26.8	50	71
2	30	108	480	600	912	1320	3.6	16	20.0	30	44
3	42	126	636	750	1002	...	3.0	15	18.8	24	...
4	54	140	822	900	1080	...	2.6	15	17.0	20	...

Mukherjee and Papaconstantinou (*Phil. Mag.*, 1922, **44**, 305) have shown that according to Smoluchowski's theory the values of the ratios T_1/T , T_2/T , etc., must be constant for every electrolyte concentration, where T , T_1 , T_2 , etc., are the respective times to reach the same stage of coalescence. An examination of the experimental data given in Table I shows that although Smoluchowski's theory applies fairly well during the earlier stages of the coagulation process, marked divergences are observed as the coagulation proceeds (*cf.* Mukherjee and Papaconstantinou, *loc. cit.*; Westgren, *Ark. Matim. Astron. Fys.*, 1918, **13**, 1014; Mukherjee and Majumdar, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, **125**, 794). Thus the values of T_1/T vary from 7.6 to 6.2, and those of T_3/T from 40.6 to 31.2.

Generally the values of the ratios T_1/T , T_2/T , etc., are continuously decreasing, showing that the rate is becoming more and more rapid than that required by the theory. The present experiments with a monodisperse sol thus do not agree with the conclusion of Westgren and Reitstotter (*loc. cit.*) that the breakdown of the Smoluchowski's theory in the case of slow coagulation is due to the polydispersity of the colloid.

In Table II, are given the values obtained with a very dilute monodisperse sulphur sol. The rate of coagulation of the above sol can be clearly followed from Fig. 2. From the figure it is apparent that the S-shaped autocatalytic nature of the curve obtained with a fairly concentrated sol, disappears completely when the sol is made fairly dilute. From Table II we find that the values of the ratios T_1/T , T_2/T , etc., are fairly constant when the coagulation is rapid, but show a distinct decrease as the rate of coagulation decreases. In the case of rapid coagulation, therefore, the results are in fair agreement with the theory, but when the case of slow coagulation is considered the above results clearly show that even when the sol is monodisperse and its rate of coagulation is not autocatalytic, Smoluchowski's theory does not hold strictly.

The sulphur sol used in the present experiments was fairly free from electrolytes as impurities. Preliminary experiments with a sample of the sol which was dialysed to remove practically all traces of electrolytes did not give any better values for the ratios. It appears, therefore, that divergences from Smoluchowski's theory cannot be satisfactorily explained as being due to traces of electrolytes in the sol.

The values for the ratios T_1/T , T_2/T , etc., during the earlier stages of coagulation, as obtained from measurements with the microphotometer and given in Table III, were also not constant but they continually decreased showing as before, that the rate of coagulation is more rapid than that required by Smoluchowski's theory.

Mecklenburg (*Kolloid Z.*, 1916, 16, 97) using colloidal sulphur has shown that the intensity of the scattered beam is proportional to the concentration of the particles in the sol so long as the diameter of the particles does not exceed 0.5μ . It is possible that the deviations observed towards the later stages of coagulation might be due to the size of the particles exceeding the Mecklenburg limit

of $95 \mu\mu$, when the intensity of the scattered beam would no longer be proportional to the velocity of coagulation. As, however, the results obtained with the Tyndallmeter are in general agreement with those obtained with the microphotometer, it is clear that the divergences from Smoluchowski's theory as obtained in the present experiments are real and are not due to any shortcomings of the experimental arrangements used.

It thus seems reasonable to conclude that all explanations based on such factors as deviations from monodispersity, presence of traces of electrolytes, etc., are inadequate to account for the divergences from Smoluchowski's theory in the region of slow coagulation.

The principal difference between slow and rapid coagulation is that in the former case the particles are only partially discharged whilst in the latter case they are nearly completely so. In the case of slow coagulation this residual electric charge on the particles is thus too important a factor to be neglected and accordingly an attempt has been made to study the problem from this point of view. The results are given in the next part of this paper.

The author wishes to express his best thanks to Dr. G. B. Banerji for the microphotometer prints and to Dr. P. B. Ganguly for the kind interest during the progress of this work.